

Teaching middle school mathematics through global perspectives: An open online course

Mahati Kopparla, UNESCO Mahatma Gandhi Institute of Education for Peace and Sustainability, University of Calgary, ✉ mahatikopparla1991@gmail.com

Akash Kumar Saini, UNESCO Mahatma Gandhi Institute of Education for Peace and Sustainability

Mathematical ideas are used across cultures to make sense of the surroundings, represent patterns, and predict future events. However, most students associate mathematics as a tool to manipulate numbers rather than a means to communicate complex ideas. To bridge this gap, an open online course was developed to introduce mathematics as a means to understand major social, political, and ecological issues in the world. The course is designed for middle school students (grades 6-8) and aims to build competence in statistics and data handling. The course content can be used to complement the existing mathematics curriculum and promote awareness about global issues. During the project presentation, we will showcase the open online course and the process of constructing the course.

Problem statement

We use mathematical ideas across cultures to make sense of our surroundings, represent patterns, and predict future events (Wagner, 2010). Some examples include (a) our representation of time through globally accepted 24 hour-days, or (b) our systems of evaluating the worth of goods and services using currency. Through the use of mathematics, we have often found ways to communicate our ideas and experiences with other people irrespective of geographical and linguistic boundaries (Orth, 2013). In fact, the scope of mathematics education to encourage active citizenship and help students understand global issues has been identified (Boylan & Coles, 2017; Renert, 2011).

However, contemporary school mathematics is designed to build a certain level of mathematical skill. Students are rarely exposed to the scope of applying their knowledge beyond classroom contexts. Even the application or story problems fit a specific template and students are taught to identify key words and perform relevant operations (Gerofsky, 2004). The emphasis on solving problems swiftly causes students to automate the process of calculation and desensitizes them to the context of the problem and meaning of the numbers (Wagner & Davis, 2010). As a result, most students associate mathematics as a tool to manipulate numbers (Davis, 2014) rather than a means to communicate complex ideas.

Please cite as: Kopparla, M., & Saini, A. K. (2021). Teaching middle school mathematics through global perspectives: An open online course. In D. Kolloosche (Ed.), *Exploring new ways to connect: Proceedings of the Eleventh International Mathematics Education and Society Conference* (Vol. 1, pp. 189–192). Tredition. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5392147>

Given this disconnect in the current system, there is a need to bridge the gap between school mathematics and the real-world. In response, we have developed an online course that introduces mathematics as a means to understand and communicate details about the major social, political, and ecological issues that our world faces today. This open online course aims to enable teachers and learners to complement the existing middle school mathematics curriculum with content that promotes awareness about global events and issues. Additionally, the project team will share the course development process which may be beneficial to other educators and researchers.

Significance

In 2015, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)—a universal call to action to end poverty, protect the planet and ensure that all people enjoy peace and prosperity was adopted by the 193 member states of the United Nations. Of the 17 SDGs, SDG 4 focuses not only on providing ‘quality, inclusive and equitable education’ – but also an education that improves people’s lives and seeks to build peaceful and sustainable societies. In order for SDG 4 to be achieved, the purpose of education needs to transform from a factory system of ‘producing economically efficient beings’, to ‘learners empowered to question inequality, unsustainability, loss of common identity and violence’. In response to this need, the open online course is an initiative towards reframing the scope of mathematics education to promote awareness about critical global issues.

Outline of the course

The course¹ will build skills in statistics and data handling. Most curriculums (Common Core Standard, NCERT, Schola Europaea) around the world emphasize on teaching about data and data handling throughout middle school. Given that data handling is the process of data (a) collection, (b) organization, (c) analysis and (d) depiction of insights with the help of graphs or charts, the course consists of four modules targeting each step of the process. In each module, with the exception of the first module, the mathematical concepts are introduced in the context of a globally significant topic. A concise module-wise outline of the course is provided in Table 1.

Module	Context
1. Introduction	NA
2. Data Organization	Comparison across countries based on government system, levels of peace, and environmental sustainability
3. Data Analysis	Occurrence and impact of natural phenomena such as earthquakes, volcanoes, and lightning
4. Data Visualization	Water on earth and the impact of climate change on water related disasters.

Table 1: Module-wise outline of the open online course

¹ Link to the complete course: <https://framerspace.com/course/BJaEOnDmI-sel-for-stem>

Process of course building

Based on the mathematical focus of the module, suitable global data was chosen to highlight the key mathematical concepts. For example, module 3 focused on natural disasters, which were particularly relevant to the course due to their global ecological impacts. To discuss the concept of median, data related to deaths from volcanic explosions was used. Amidst the variety of data related to volcanic explosion, death rate could uniquely demonstrate the need for median due to the large variability within the data. Similarly, relevant data was selected from open sources for each module context (shown in Table 1).

The overall course construction process was based on the UDL planning process for instruction (Rao & Meo, 2016). Five pedagogical tools, namely, (i) storytelling; (ii) gamification; (iii) inquiry; (iv) reflection; and (v) dialogue were employed to design an engaging multisensory learning experience (Rautela & Singh, 2019). In line with the 7 design principles of UDL (Burgstahler, 2009), the following design considerations were used throughout the course to provide a conducive digital learning space.

Clear instructions and ease of Navigation

As the course was completely online, providing clear and simple instructions for students was key to sustain engagement. The course materials were colour coded to indicate the expected learner actions (as shown in Figure 1). Links to navigate through the course pages were made easily accessible through a course map.

Figure 1: Example of a course page with instructions and a course map button.

Interactive and flexible delivery methods

The overall tone of the course was a dialogue with a peer rather than an instructor. The course had several mathematical characters, with the most prominent being Addy – a companion for students going through the course. The different modules within the course were designed as interactive conversations that the student could have with the various

characters, offering them the flexibility to engage with the concept. Elements of storytelling were used to introduce, explain, and explore ideas to creating an imaginative and emotional experience for the learners.

Self-paced content exploration

Following an inquiry-based approach, each lesson started with an observation or question that Addy brings up. Students were encouraged to explore the question through a variety of activities and digital tools. They were provided the opportunity to choose their learning trajectory with links to review older content, seek alternative explanations or engage with external sources for additional information.

Gamified feedback and assessments

Games were used to help students reinforce new concepts. Gamification or using elements of games within activities was to motivate progress through the learning material and provide the learners with opportunities for reflection. Based on their responses, learners received feedback and suggestions to engage with certain learning materials. The course not only tolerated error, but also used error as a learning opportunity rather than learning assessment.

Acknowledgement

We wish to thank UNESCO MGIEP, the institute where this project was developed.

References

- Boylan, M., & Coles, A. T. (2017). Is another mathematics education possible? An introduction to a Special Issue on Mathematics Education and the Living World. *Philosophy of Mathematics Education Journal*, 32.
- Burgstahler, S. (2009). Universal design in education: Principles and applications. *DO-IT*.
- Davis, B. (2014). Toward a more power-full school mathematics. *For the Learning of Mathematics*, 34(1), 12–17.
- Gerofsky, S. (2004). *A man left Albuquerque heading east: Word problems as genre in mathematics education*. New York: Peter Lang.
- Orth, B. (2013, May). *Mathematics orality and literacy*. Portland State University Library. <https://pdxscholar.library.pdx.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1027&context=studentsymposium>
- Rautela, R., & Singh, N. C. (2019). Libre: Nourish the brain so the future can flourish. *Childhood Education*, 95(5), 34–43.
- Rao, K., & Meo, G. (2016). Using universal design for learning to design standards-based lessons. *Sage Open*, 6(4), 1–12.
- Renert, M. (2011). Mathematics for life: Sustainable mathematics education. *For the Learning of Mathematics*, 31(1), 20–26.
- Wagner, D. (2010). If mathematics is a language, how do you swear in it. *The Best Writing on Mathematics*, 6(3), 449–457.
- Wagner, D., & Davis, B. (2010). Feeling number: Grounding number sense in a sense of quantity. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 74(1), 39–51.